

Evaluation of the level of Job Safety in some selected Organizations in Kampala, Uganda.

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ABSTRACT

This research evaluated the level of job safety in some selected organizations in Kampala, Uganda. The study objective was achieved through descriptive, Cross sectional and correlative survey designs. A study population of 484 was used, from which a sample population of 219 respondents was derived using Slovene's Formula. Data was collected primarily using Self-Administered Questionnaires (SAQs) and structured Interviews. Findings revealed that the level of job safety in selected Public and Private Organizations in Kampala, Uganda was high with (mean = 2.97); implying that private and public organizations in Uganda have high levels of job safety in terms of electronic and fire safety, sanitation, tools and equipment and protection from hazardous materials. Comparatively, sanitation ranked highest among all elements of job safety, in terms of whether food is separated from hazardous materials with (mean = 3.46, std. dev = .720) interpreted as very high. The last ranked item was about whether smoke detectors function properly with (mean = 2.44, std. dev = 1.062) interpreted as high. In conclusion, the level of job safety among Public and Private organizations in Kampala, Uganda was high. This means that private and public organizations in Uganda have high levels of job safety in terms of electronic and fire safety, sanitation, tools and equipment and protection from hazardous materials. This study recommends that different stakeholders including government and Non-governmental Organizations need to put in place mechanisms to ensure that employees are protected from work. The government should put in place laws aiming at protecting workers against health issues associated with work related Hazards.

Keywords: Job Safety, selected, public and private Organizations.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, Job safety has not been given attention by both public and private organizations for purposes of not affecting their profitability. Within the past 30 years, issues of employee safety have increased due to increased disasters in organizations (e.g., Chernobyl, Upper Big-Branch Mine, Davis-Besse etc.) [1, 2, 3, 4]. Globally, the regulatory framework in the European countries facilitates participatory psychosocial interventions [5, 6, 7]. Further, the European Framework Directive on Safety and Health at Work (Directive 89/391 EEC) makes employee safety concerns mandatory for the employer in order to ensure safety of employees in

work related aspects [8, 9, 10]. Additionally, the regulatory framework enhances the need to implement participative approaches in occupational health [11, 12]. In the previous two decades, most European countries recognized the right of employees to participate in occupational health through the EU Framework Directive 1989/391. Nonetheless, in most countries, the level of transposition of the Directive has been inadequate. Worse still, legislation of many member countries lack detailed regulatory expression of key issues including: level of responsibility of employers on occupational safety; coverage and

election of occupational safety representatives; the compulsory need to assess workplace occupational hazards; the need to enforce occupational health services; the mandatory need to register occupational hazards on all organizations, consultation, training; and participation by workers [13, 14, 15].

The 19th century and first half of the 20th century witnessed rapid economical, technical and social changes. There is generally an ongoing mechanization, triggered by a movement to rationalize production. Occupational safety is increasingly developing into a professional field [16, 17, 18]. Most remarkably, organizations are enclosing hazards and fencing heights, shaping up safety techniques, and writing practical publications on occupational safety. Several professionals and scholars including Sociologists, psychologists, and physicians are more concerned with issues regarding accident causation, and are engaged in research leading to different safety theories [19, 20, 21, 23]. Two assumptions attempt to explain Causes of occupational accident; either the workers' capacity to handle hazardous situations, or in external causes, for instance long

Conceptual Background

The subject of safety in the workplace covers a wide spectrum of issues. Among them are issues such as; Working with hazardous chemicals and minerals [31,32,33,34], Exposure to contagious diseases and passive smoking [35], Psychological safety such as stress, fears and attitudes [36], Psychosocial safety such as indifference, xenophobia, homophobia and lesbophobia [37], Criminal and sexual harassment in the workplace [38], Working within harmful workplace emissions [39], Manufactured and manufacturing of harmful substances and innovations [40], Harmful infrastructural constructions such as unsafe stairways, unsafely built structures and slippery floors [41].

Theoretical Background

This study was guided by Maslow theory of needs. It is a theory in psychology, proposed by Abraham Maslow in his 1943 paper "A theory of Human

working hours, dangerous machines and the increased pressures of work and speed of production [24, 25]. The Pittsburgh survey, the first extended analysis of occupational accidents in a steel district, strongly advocated the environmental hypothesis, while the so-called 'individual hypothesis' is favored by the American Safety First Movement, starting as a private initiative in 1906 by US Steel, and later spreading out over Western European countries [26, 27]. The British Industrial Fatigue Board has given the individual hypothesis its scientific justification. Despite scientific criticism just after World War II on the concept of accident proneness and 'unsafe acts', its popularity is not fading. Even nowadays the famous metaphors are still part of the vocational training of safety experts, also in The Netherlands [28, 29, 30]. Apparently professional and scientific developments in occupational safety are belonging to two separate worlds. Before World War II, The Netherlands was not a leading country in occupational safety but a follower, first of France and the German speaking countries. After World War I its focus is directed towards the Anglo-Saxon countries.

Terroristic intrusions and massacres in the workplace [41] and Safety precautions, safety communication measures and personal protection equipment [39, 40, 41]. In this study the researcher conceptualized job safety in terms of electric safety, fire safety, hazardous materials, sanitation and tools and equipment's safety. In organizations, occupational accidents may arise from three dimensions: the task to be done, for instance malfunctioning machines, lack of protective equipment like working conditions which arise from inadequate lighting, fatigue that comes out of excessive working hours and the employee himself/herself.

Motivation'~ It states that Human needs have bearing on motivation. It in other words state that human beings are motivated by unsatisfied needs, and that

certain lower factors need to be satisfied before higher needs can be satisfied. Maslow subsequently extended the idea to include his observations of human's innate curiosity. Maslow use the terms physiological, safety, belongingness and love, and self-actualization needs to describe the pattern that human motivation generally move through [30]. Maslow's hierarchy of needs is often portrayed in the shape of a pyramid, with the largest and most fundamental levels of needs at the bottom and the need for actualization at the top [20].

According to Maslow, there are general types of needs (physiological, survival, safety, love, and esteem) that must be satisfied before a person can act

unselfishly. He called these needs "deficiency needs." As long as we are motivated to satisfy these cravings, we are moving towards growth, toward self-actualization. Satisfying needs is healthy, while preventing gratification makes us sick or act evilly. Maslow's hierarchy of needs is often portrayed in the shape of a pyramid with the largest, most fundamental levels of needs at the bottom and the need for self-actualization at the top. While the pyramid has become the de facto way to represent the hierarchy, Maslow himself never used a pyramid to describe these levels in any of his writings on the subject.

Contextual background

Precautions, safety communication and personal protective equipment (P.P.E) and reflects on how workers at organizational performance, engage with and respond towards the occupational safety and health administration measures thus contributing to own job safety and employee performance in the organizations at workplace. Productivity enhancement is sometimes tied to gender equality at workplace, equal pay for work of equal value, skilling, adaptation to technology and a culture of

productive competitiveness, innovation and creativity. Non-discrimination on the basis of known or perceived HIV status, HIV counseling and testing, greater involvement of people living with HIV, promotion of prevention, treatment, care and support will increase productivity and eliminate stigma. The interaction of health hazards and the human organisms can occur either through the senses, by absorption through the skin, by intake into the digestive tract via the mouth or by inhalation into the lungs.

Aim of the study

The aim of this research was to examine the level of job safety in some selected Organizations in Kampala, Uganda.

Research Question

- i. What is the level of Job Safety among selected Organizations in Kampala, Uganda?

Geographical Scope

This study was confined to the Makerere University, Mukwano Industry, and National Organization of Teachers Association.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive Cross sectional and correlative survey design. It was descriptive study which is non-experimental. It describes the characteristics of a particular individual, or of a group.

Research Population

The target population of this study consisted of 484 respondents from Mukwano Industry, Makerere University, National Organization of teachers associations.

Sample Size

To get the sample size of 219 respondents; Mukwano Industry, Makerere University staffs, and national organization of teachers association were got from these sample categories.

Table 1: shows the respondents of the study with the following categories: The Sloven's formula is used to determine the minimum sample size

Table 1: Respondents of the Study

Category of Employees	Accessible Population	Sample Size	Sampling Method
Mukwano Industry	120	54	Simple Random
Makerere University Administrators	220	100	Simple Random
National Association of teachers	144	64	Simple Random
Total	484	219	

Source: Researcher (2014)

Table 1: the above shows the criteria for selection of the respondents

$$n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2}$$

Where: n = sample size, N = accessible population size, e = margin of error.

$$n = \frac{484}{1+(484)0.05^2} \quad n = 219$$

Sampling Procedures

The sampling technique in this research was simple random sampling. This is because, it is free from bias and therefore likely to led to valid observation and

generalizations. If the sample is selected well, it would be a representative of the entire population.

Research Instruments Questionnaire

A standardized self-administered questionnaire on job safety and employee productivity in public and private organizations in selected organizations in Kampala was used to determine the level of job safety and employee productivity. The scoring system of this questionnaire is as follows: strongly agree (4); agree (3); disagree (2); strongly disagree (1). The

questionnaire was divided into three parts or section, where the first section contained items on demographic characteristics of respondents, second section contained items on determining the level of employee productivity. The researcher also used an interview guide to have a clear cut understanding of the variables.

Interviews

Interviews offered a rich source of data [8] interview guide was used to explore on the job safety and employees' productivity among public and private Organizations in Kampala. It gave a platform for illiterate respondents who were part of the target population to express their views. This instrument was selected because offered trust and understanding with respondents and data was collected using a Semi-structured interview guide which contained an open ended questions. The

researcher was able to elicit information relating to their category of employment. In this case, Mukwano industry employees, Makerere University administrators and National Association of teachers enabled researcher to access non formal information and it provided to transit to formal to establish the different job safety and employee productivity among public and private organizations in Kampala. It helped the researcher to attain for information in the interview carried out.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments Reliability

To test for reliability, Cronbach's Alpha was used. The researcher measured internal consistence by using Cronbach's

Alpha. The results from the measure of reliability are shown in table 2 below.

Table 2: Reliability statistics of different constructs of the questionnaire

Constructs	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Electronic Safety	4	0.721
Fire Safety	6	0.846
Hazardous materials	7	0.884
Sanitation	4	0.761
Tools and equipments	6	0.867
Time management	5	0.551
Leadership and motivation	8	0.819
Overall	40	0.778

Source: Researcher (2014)

Overall, the results indicate that the research tool was reliable in measuring

the variable since the overall reliability was above 0.6.

Validity

It measures the extent to which a research instrument measures what it is intended to measure or the extent to which the research findings can be generalized to other populations. To test the validity of the instrument, the researcher used first inter-judge co-

efficiency of validity. Three expert judges (in this case three lecturers of the researcher) made independent appraisal of the items in the questionnaire. Their results were used to establish the content validity Index (CVI) using the following formula;

Data Gathering Procedures

Before the administration of the questionnaires

1. An introduction letter was obtained from the College of Higher Degrees and Research for the researcher to solicit approval to conduct the study from respective Ministry of education, Makerere University, Organisation of national association of teachers.
2. When approved, the researcher secured a list of the respondents from Mukwano Industry, Makerere University, Organisation of national association of teachers and were selected through random sampling from this list to arrive at the minimum sample size.
3. The respondents were explained to about the study and were requested to sign the Informed Consent Form.
4. The researcher produced more than enough questionnaires for distribution.
5. The researcher selected research assistants who assisted in the data collection. They were briefed and oriented in order to be consistent in administering the questionnaires.

During the administration of the questionnaires

1. The respondents were requested to answer completely and not to leave any part of the questionnaires unanswered.
2. The researcher and assistants emphasized retrieval of the questionnaires within five days from the date of distribution.
3. On retrieval, all returned questionnaires were checked if all are answered

After the administration of the questionnaires

The data gathered were collated, encoded into the computer and statistically treated using the frequencies and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The data processing was the presentation of every level taken to structure and analyze the collected data. This was both qualitative

and quantitative methods necessary for different ways of analyzing questionnaires and interviews. Interviews offered a rich source of data [5], interview guide was used to explore on the job safety and employees' productivity among public and private Organizations in Kampala. It gave a

platform for illiterate respondents who were part of the target population to express their views. This instrument was selected because offered trust and understanding with respondents and data was collected using a Semi-structured interview guide which contained an open ended questions. The researcher was able to elicit information relating to their category of employment. In this case, Mukwano industry

employees, Makerere University administrators and National Association of teachers enabled researcher to access non formal information and it provided to transit to formal to establish the different job safety and employee productivity among public and private organizations in Kampala. It helped the researcher to attain for information in the interview carried out.

Data Analysis

The mean and standard deviations were applied for job safety and employee productivity in organizations. Analysis of Variance was applied in establishing differences in Job safety measures as well as employee productivity in Private and Public Organizations. This was both qualitative and quantitative methods necessary for different ways of analyzing questionnaires and interviews. To determine the relationship between job safety and employee's productivity, the researcher used correlation and regression analysis. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was applied and later the

linear regression analysis was modeled between these variables. Thematic content analysis was used to expand and establish the relation between job safety and employee productivity in organization in Kampala. The researcher established a set of categories and then compiled the information that was found in specific categories. An item analysis was used to illustrate the strengths and weaknesses based on the indicators in terms of mean and rank. From these strengths and weaknesses, the recommendations were derived.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure confidentiality of the information provided by the respondents and to ascertain the practice of ethics in this study, the following activities were implemented by the researcher:

1. The respondents were coded instead of reflecting the names through a written request to the concerned officials in order to access data from them
2. The researcher requested the respondents to sign the informed

consent form specifically, participants were informed about the aim and nature of the research

3. The researcher acknowledged the authors quoted in the study through citations and referencing.
4. Findings to the study were presented in a generalized manner to enhance privacy and confidentiality.

Limitations of the Study

In view of the following threats to validity, the researcher will claim an allowable 5% margin of error. Mitigating measures were taken to minimize if not to eradicate threats to validity of findings of the study as shown below;

Extraneous variables which were beyond the researchers control such as

respondents honesty, personal biases and uncontrolled setting of the study.

Instrumentation: The research instruments are not standardized. Therefore a validity and reliability test was done to produce credible measurements of the research variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Levels of Job Safety among Public and Private Organizations in Kampala, Uganda

The objective of this study was to examine the levels of Job Safety among Public and Private Organizations in Kampala, Uganda. To achieve this objective the researcher analyzed section A of the questionnaire whose items were concerned with the level of

job safety. This section was divided into five constructs: electric safety (with four items), fire safety (with 6 items), hazardous materials (with seven items), sanitation (with 4 items) and tools and equipment (with six items), all based on a four Likert scale where 1 = strongly

disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = agree and 4 = strongly agree. The researcher used means and standard deviations to

achieve this objective. The results are shown in Tables 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 that follows:

Table 3a: Electric Safety

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank	Interpretation
Outlets and equipment are properly grounded	3.10	.821	1	High
Power cords are safe enough	3.01	.917	2.5	High
Extension cords are used only occasionally	3.01	.891	2.5	High
Power strips provided with surge protectors	2.93	.932	4	High
Overall Mean	3.0125			High

Source: Primary Data (2014)

3b: Interpretation

Mean range	Response range	Interpretation
3.26 - 4.00	Strongly agree	Very high
2.51 - 3.25	Agree	High
1.76 - 2.50	Disagree	Low
1.00 - 1.75	Strongly disagree	Very low

Table 3 illustrated the response means of electronic safety as one of the constructs of job safety in public and private organizations in Kampala Uganda. The result in the table show that, concerning whether outlets and equipment are properly grounded in employees workplaces was ranked the highest with (mean = 3.10, Std. Dev = .821) interpreted as high. In terms of whether power cords are safe enough and whether extension cords are used only occasionally, these had the same means (mean = 3.01) interpreted as high. Their standard deviations were (std. dev = 0.917) and (std. dev = .891) respectively. This however shows that there is a high deviation from the mean for "Power cords are safe enough" compared to "Extension cords are used only occasionally". The last ranked item under this construct was whether Power strips provided with surge protectors in work places with

(mean = 2.93) interpreted as high. The overall level of electronic safety was high with (mean = 3.01). Interpreted as high, indicating that some that there was the level of job safety among public and private organizations in Kampala, Uganda as was identified by some of the respondents in their voices as indicated below:

"Being in this organization tot a long period of time, I have never experienced any electric surge problem and power cords are safe enough because the outlets and equipment are properly ground by our technicians"

To this investigation, indicates that there was the level of electric safety in the selected organizations that took part in the study which included Makerere University, Mukwano industry and Association of National teachers in Kampala, Uganda.

Table 4a: Fire Safety

Items	Mean	Std.	Rank	Interpretati
Locations of fire extinguishers visible	3.29	.962	1	Very High
Fire exits are visible enough	3.02	1.041	2	High
Fire extinguishers are up to date regarding inspections	2.98	1.025	3	High
Fire exits are unblocked	2.87	1.050	4	High
Fire evacuation plan visible enough	2.67	1.093	5	High
The smoke detectors function properly	2.44	1.062	6	High
Overall Mean	2.878			High

Source: Primary Data (2014)

4b: Interpretation

Mean range	Response range	Interpretation
3.26 - 4.00	Strongly agree	Very high
2.51 - 3.25	Agree	High
1.76 - 2.50	Disagree	Low
1.00 - 1.75	Strongly disagree	Very low

Result in Table 4. Shows the response means of fire safety - one of the constructs of job safety. The first ranked item under this construct was whether Locations of fire extinguishers visible to employees with (mean = 3.29, std. dev = .962) interpreted as very high. This means that employees easily see the locations of fire extinguishers and therefore can easily reach for them in times of need. The item on whether fire exist are visible enough in case of the need to rush out of workplace in case of fire, this was ranked second with (mean = 3.02, Std. Dev= 1.041) interpreted as high. in terms of whether Fire extinguishers are up to date regarding inspections, this was ranked third with (mean = 2.98, std. dev = 1.025) interpreted as high. The item concerning whether fire exist are unblocked in case of need to rush out of the work place, this was ranked fourth with (mean = 2.87, std. dev = 1.050) interpreted as high. The item concerning whether fire evacuation plan(s) is (are) visible enough, this was ranked fifth with (mean = 2.67, std. dev = 1.093) interpreted as high. The last ranked item under this construct was about whether smoke detectors function

properly with (mean = 2.44, std. dev = 1.062) interpreted as high. The overall mean of fire safety was (mean = 2.878) interpreted as high meaning that there is a relationship between job safety and employee productivity as greed by the respondents in the selected organizations where the study took place. This finding is similar to what was found in the interviews as reflected in 'the voice of one of the respondents:

"I have worked this organization for the last 10 years but what I have seen with my eyes is that we have fire are update to standards which makes our Jobs safe"

In the same interview one of employee who has work for two years who narrates that " compared to other organization which offered me employment, Am overwhelmed by this organization's fire safety that makes me safe with no worry for fire because of the type of fire extinguishers that are put in place for my safety but still needs for to be put in every corner of the organization."

Most of the employees in the selected study found themselves safe and happy with the measures that the organizations have put in place for their safety.

Table 5a: Hazardous Materials

Items	Mean	Std.	Ran	Interpretati
Food is separated from hazardous materials	3.46	.720	1	Very High
Labels of the hazardous materials visible	3.21	.905	2	High
There are special storage places for hazardous materials	3.17	.925	3	High
People wear safety gear when they handle hazardous materials	2.94	1.003	4	High
Disposal of hazardous materials is safe process	2.89	.987	5	High
Handlers of hazardous materials trained properly	2.85	.925	6	High
Safety gear for working with hazardous materials near by	2.82	.996	7	High
Overall Mean	3.049			High

Source: Primary Data (2014)

5b: Interpretation

Mean range	Response range	Interpretation
3.26 - 4.00	Strongly agree	Very high
2.51 - 3.25	Agree	High
1.76 - 2.50	Disagree	Low
1.00 - 1.75	Strongly disagree	Very low

The third construct of job safety was concerned with the employees protection or safety from hazardous materials. The findings in the Table 5 show the results from analysis by the use of means of the responses concerning this. The results indicate that concerning whether Food is separated from hazardous materials was ranked the highest with (mean = 3.46, std. dev = .720) interpreted as very high. Concerning whether Labels of the hazardous materials visible, this was ranked second with (mean = 3.21, std. dev = .905) interpreted as high. In terms of whether there are special storage places for hazardous materials, this was ranked third with (mean = 3.17, std. dev = .925) interpreted as high. The fourth ranked item was "People wear safety gear when they handle hazardous materials" with (mean = 2.94, std. dev = 1.003) interpreted as high. The item "Disposal of hazardous materials is safe process" was ranked 5th with (mean = 2.89, std. dev = .987) interpreted as high. Concerning whether handlers of

hazardous materials trained properly, this was ranked 5th with (mean = 2.85, std. dev = .925) interpreted as high. The last ranked item under this construct was about whether Safety gear for working with hazardous materials nearby with (mean = 2.82, std. dev = .996) interpreted as high. The overall job safety in terms of protection from hazardous materials, this was rated high with (mean = 3.049) interpreted as high meaning that the level of Hazardous materials is a big concern due to a high level of precautions as a serious issue to job safety and employee productivity among public and private organizations which took part in the study. The respondents noted that:

"Hazardous materials especially in Mukwano industry was a big concern that the organization has taken serious with a lot of measures in the organisation".

Therefore, the voices of the interview show that Hazardous material if not taken with serious measures it can affect job safety and employee productivity

among public and private organizations in Kampala, Uganda.

Table 6a: Sanitation

Items	Mean	Std. deviation	Rank	Interpretation
Dining area always clean	3.36	.827	1	Very High
Restrooms clean enough	3.15	.848	2	High
There is always enough soaps and towels for employees	2.67	1.029	3	High
Workplace is protected from rodents and insects	2.61	1.022	4	High
Overall Mean	2.95			High

Source: Primary Data (2014)

6b: Interpretation

Mean range	Response range	Interpretation
3.26 - 4.00	Strongly agree	Very high
2.51 - 3.25	Agree	High
1.76 - 2.50	Disagree	Low
1.00 - 1.75	Strongly disagree	Very low

Results in table 6 show the mean responses on sanitation as one of the constructs of job safety. Poor sanitation can lead to chronic diseases such as cholera which may hinder employees' productivity. The highest ranked item was about whether dining area is always clean with (mean = 3.36, std. dev = .827) interpreted as very high. The second highest ranked item was concerned with whether restrooms are clean enough with (mean = 3.15, std. dev = .848) interpreted as high. The item "There is always enough soaps and towels for employees" was ranked 3rd with (mean = 2.67, std. dev = 1.029) interpreted as high. The last ranked item was concerned with whether workplace is protected from rodents and insects with (mean = 2.61, std. dev = 1.022) interpreted as high. The overall mean concerning sanitation was high (mean = 2.95) meaning the interpretation is high. It indicates that the majority of

the respondents in the interview said that sanitation is high a part from few employees who said that sanitation was very high meaning that few employees were strongly agreed but the question of the majority of the respondents who said they agree meaning it was high and hesitated with some few issues that sanitation was not very satisfactory as was quoted by one of the respondents as: *"We women need more than enough to do with sanitation part because we women have no provision for where we can put our pads in case of emergence"* The study found out that organizations that were party of the study had tried to improve on the sanitation as part of job safety and employee productivity among public and private organizations in Kampala, Uganda but not hesitated that sanitation was not enough for their job safety.

Table 7a:Tools and Equipments

Item	Mean	Std.	Ran	Interpretation
When not used, hand tools kept in special places	3.34	.780	1	Very High
Machine operators well trained	3.11	.783	2	High
When working with machinery, the safety gear is always available	2.90	.917	3	High
People that work with machinery wear proper safety gear	2.85	.981	4	High
Machines used are completely functional	2.79	.937	5	High
They keep the safety guards for moving parts in special places	2.76	.937	6	High
Overall Mean	2.96			High
General Mean	2.97			High

Source: Primary Data (2014)

7b:Interpretation

Mean range	Response range	Interpretation
3.26 - 4.00	Strongly agree	Very high
2.51 - 3.25	Agree	High
1.76 - 2.50	Disagree	Low
1.00 - 1.75	Strongly disagree	Very low

The last construct under job safety was the safety of tools and equipment used at work or during work. Table 7 shows the mean responses of this construct. The results show that, concerning whether hand tools when not used are kept in safe places, this was ranked the highest with (mean = 3.34, std. dev = .780) interpreted as very high. In terms of whether machine operators are well trained, this was ranked second with (mean = 3.11, std. dev = .783) interpreted as high. The item "When working with machinery, the safety gear is always available" was ranked 3rd with (mean = 2.90, std. dev = .917) interpreted as high. Concerning whether People that work with machinery wear proper safety gear, this was ranked 4th with (mean = 2.85, std. dev = .981) interpreted as high. The fifth ranked item was "machines used are completely functional" with (mean = 2.79, std. dev =

.937) interpreted as high. The last ranked item was employees keep the safety guards for moving parts in special places with (mean = 2.76, std. dev = .937) interpreted as high. The overall mean concerning tools and equipment was (mean = 2.96) interpreted as high.

Generally, the overall level of job safety among Public and Private Organizations in Kampala, Uganda was high with (mean = 2.97) interpreted as high. This means that private and public organizations in Uganda have high levels of job safety in terms of electronic and fire safety, sanitation, tools and equipment and protection from hazardous materials. The overall highly ranked item was concerned with sanitation, that is whether food is separated from hazardous materials was ranked the highest with (mean = 3.46, std. dev = .720) interpreted as very high. The last

ranked item was about whether smoke detectors function properly with (mean = 2.44, std. dev = 1.062) interpreted as high.

The interviews indicated that tools and equipment used at work or during work was are good and functioning which was quoted by the respondents who took part in the study as:

"All the tools we use are kept well in separate places and some machines we use are functioning well so we don't find any problem with them, they make our work simple to produce results"

The study found out that tools and equipment were ranged high by the respondents, it indicates that tools and machine equipment by job safety show that there is a strong relationship between job safety and productivity of

The level of job safety among Public and Private Organizations in Kampala, Uganda was high. This means that private and public organizations in Uganda have high levels of job safety in terms of electronic and fire safety, sanitation, tools and equipment and

Depending on the findings, the researcher recommended the following: Different stakeholders (government, NGOs) in different organisations need to ensure that employees are protected

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employees among public and private organizations in Kampala, Uganda.

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CONCLUSION

protection from hazardous materials. The overall highly ranked item was concerned with sanitation that is whether food is separated from hazardous materials. This means that food is always kept safe from such materials that may infect the food and thus harm workers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

from such health problems associated with work. The government should put in place laws aiming at protecting workers against health issues associated with their work.

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